

ENHANCED FLOW MONITORING IN RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING USING ELECTRICAL IMPEDANCE TOMOGRAPHY WITH EMBEDDED CARBON NANOTUBE SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

One of the most common methods to fabricate composite materials is the resin transfer molding (RTM) process. The final part quality is influenced by multiple factors, generally divided into two key categories: resin flow issues and fiber misalignment. Typical flow issues are incomplete wetting, resin starvation, and resin pooling, whilst misalignment includes fiber shifting and fiber washout. Additionally, the placement of vacuum vents must be controlled so that resin travels to those last (which helps ensure full impregnation of the part before excess material is removed). Failure to address these parameters can lead to race tracking, where dry spots form unpredictably from one trial to the next. Thus, monitoring the flow of resin in real-time and adapting it during the process is essential to reduce voids and defects detrimental to composite performance. Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) is one such promising approach that uses boundary electrodes and steady DC current to generate an impedance-based map of resin flowing through the fabric. Figure 1 illustrates the two most common patterns for current injection and voltage measurement. Each approach has its own strengths and limitations. The adjacent pattern offers a simpler setup with higher sensitivity at the edges but reduced sensitivity in the center of the sensor. Conversely, the opposite pattern provides improved sensitivity across the entire sensor, including the center, but requires more advanced software for data processing and analysis. In this paper, both approaches, will be implemented and compared to identify the optimal EIT technique for real-time applications. EIT addresses such issues by real-time enabling flow monitoring through embedded carbon nanotube-based sensing elements that further assist adaptive process control towards obtaining composite parts of high quality and without defects.

Figure 1: Most common injection and measurement patterns to implement Electrical Impedance Tomography (a) Adjacent (b) Opposite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer molding (RTM) enables cost efficient fabrication of high-performance fiber reinforced polymer composites, yet the closed mold geometry masks the evolving resin front and leaves the process vulnerable to dry spots, race tracking, and resin pooling [1]. Those defects can reduce in plane strength by more than 30 % and often go undetected until final inspection [2, 3]. Conventional point sensors—thermocouples, dielectric probes or fiber optics—report resin arrival only at discrete locations, so critical regions between sensors may still be unmonitored. Electrical Impedance Tomography (EIT) offers a distributed alternative by injecting low-amplitude current through boundary electrodes and measuring boundary voltages. The spatial conductivity field inside a conductive skin can then be reconstructed in real-time.

Our group previously demonstrated [4, 5, 6] that non-woven glass veils coated with a thin carbon nanotube (CNT) network can act simultaneously as a flexible sensing layer in composite laminates. When the network is dry it exhibits a percolation-based baseline conductivity; once impregnated, resin increases the CNT to CNT tunnelling distance, dropping the local conductivity by one to two orders of magnitude [7]. By tracking these changes with EIT we convert the veil into a quasi-continuous flow sensor. The present work extends that concept in three ways. First, we manufactured the CNT and tested them with localized compression tests by applying weights on the veil. Second, we evaluated both the adjacent and opposite drive–measurement patterns outlined in Figure 1 in order to quantify resolution and noise sensitivity across the entire sensor. Finally, we coupled the sensor output to high speed Gauss–Newton reconstruction in EIDORS, achieving a demonstration of the resin flow during Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Carbon-Nanotube-Based Veil Sensor Fabrication

Multi-wall CNTs (Nanocyl AQ0303) were deposited onto non-woven glass veils supplied by Technical Fiber Products (TFP). In this work, 34 g m^{-2} was selected to match the mechanical compliance of the composite plies while remaining electrically insulating. To create a conductive network, a 3 wt % dispersion of the CNTs in aqueous sizing was diluted 1:2 with ultrapure water (target 1 wt % CNT), deagglomerated for 60 s in a THINKY® ARM 310 planetary mixer at 2000 rpm and then sonicated for 30 min in a Branson 1510 bath. Rectangular coupons were dip-coated for 20 min per side, followed by 15 min drying at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a convection oven. Baseline sheet resistance ranged from $50 \text{ }\Omega$ to $2 \text{ k}\Omega$. Thus, the originally non-conductive glass veil becomes a thin, flexible electrode layer suitable for EIT interrogation of resin flow or mechanical compaction.

Sixteen $1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ electrodes were stencil printed around the perimeter with silver paint (SPI Supplies) as seen in Figure 2, oven dried 30 min at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, then wired using a low resistivity Ag epoxy (EPOXIES 40 3900) and cured 1 h at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; the epoxy’s conductivity ($10^{-4} \text{ }\Omega \text{ cm}$) is negligible compared with the veil.

Figure 2: Photo of the 16-electrode system CNT coated glass veil sensors.

2.2 Compression Testing

As explained in Section 1, a carbon nanotube (CNT) veil derives its sensing capability from changes in the quantum tunnelling resistance between neighboring nanotubes. Any external stimulus that alters the inter particle spacing modulates the network conductivity and can therefore be imaged with electrical impedance tomography (EIT). Performing a full RTM or VARTM run each time we tune the EIT reconstruction parameters would be prohibitively slow, consume substantial materials, and yield results that are difficult to reproduce under identical conditions. To obtain rapid, repeatable feedback, we instead apply a controlled out of plane compressive load to the sensor as seen in Figure 3. Compressive loads of up to 10 kilonewton (kN) were applied with an Instron 5985 universal testing machine. The force was delivered through rigid polycarbonate blocks—one square and one circular seen in the figure—to confine the pressure to a well-defined region of the CNT veil. Resistance change due to the compression at every electrode was logged continuously throughout each loading sequence. Compaction modifies the CNT tunnelling distances in a well-defined manner, producing a conductivity change that EIT can resolve.

Figure 3: (a) Compression testing setup showing the connected sensors, and the loading cell in Instron (b) Close-up picture showing the circular loading block used to apply local pressure.

Once the inversion parameters have been optimized using this compression tests, a VARTM trial is carried out to validate the customized EIT algorithm by reconstructing the actual resin flow field.

2.3 Composite Lay-up and VARTM Procedure

The CNT veil was placed directly beneath the peel ply so that wiring exited the bag edge. A nylon flow media layer and standard bag film completed the stack. To minimize air leakage we adopted a double-tacky-tape seal (can be seen in Figure 4) each electrode wire was first sandwiched between two parallel strips of tacky tape, then a second continuous bead was laid outside this pair to give a redundant barrier. The lay-up was vacuumed and held for 2 h to let the fiber stack compact and relax before infusion. With the vacuum still applied, EPON 862/ Epikure W resin was drawn in from the inlet side while the far edge remained vented. The experiment was filmed at 60 fps through the transparent bag, and resistance/voltage was logged simultaneously from all electrodes for later EIT reconstruction.

Figure 4: Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding Setup with Electrical Impedance Tomography sensor.

2.4 Data Acquisition and Electrical Impedance Tomography

The sensor was driven by a 16 channel source–measure unit that injected 10 mA DC according to either the adjacent or opposite pattern (Fig. 1). Sixteen surface electrodes were driven sequentially with a 10 mA DC stimulus, cycling the source pair around the perimeter in either the adjacent or opposite configuration. During each injection no potentials were recorded on the two current-carrying electrodes, and any adjacent-voltage lead that shared one of those electrodes was also omitted to avoid contact-noise amplification; this leaves $16-3=13$ usable adjacent differences per drive. One full rotation therefore yields $16 \times 13 = 208$ independent boundary voltages per frame, a data set large enough for robust inversion yet compact enough for near–real-time operation once redundant reciprocity measurements are eliminated. The voltages were streamed to MATLAB® and inverted in EIDORS on a 128-element triangular mesh using a single iteration of the Gauss–Newton method with zero th order Tikhonov regularization ($\lambda = 0.01$). The Jacobian J relates small conductivity perturbations $\Delta\sigma$ to voltage changes ΔV ; the update follows

$$\Delta\sigma = (J^T J + \lambda^2 I)^{-1} J^T \Delta V \quad (1)$$

which minimizes the L^2 norm of the residual while suppressing noise amplified modes [8]. Difference imaging relative to a baseline (dry state or zero load frame) removed static contact resistances.

Data were acquired with a Keithley 6430 sub-femtoamp remote SourceMeter® (current drive), a Keithley 2182A nanovoltmeter (electrode potentials), and a Keithley 3706A switcher/multiplexer (rapid electrode routing), all orchestrated in LabVIEW. The 6430 supplied the 10 mA current while the 2182A, isolated from common-mode noise, measured the resulting differential voltages. In the present script the switcher steps through 256 electrode combinations in 11 s, giving an effective 23.3 Hz measurement rate (≈ 43 ms per reading) and yielding one complete EIT frame of 208 voltages every ≈ 9 s. Parallel read-back, burst-mode switching and reduced, information-optimal drive patterns are being investigated to push the frame rate toward true real-time operation.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Sensor Morphology

Scanning electron micrographs in Figure 5 of the dip coated veil reveal a continuous CNT film that bridges individual glass fibers and creates an interconnected percolation network. It shows the randomly distributed CNTs on the surface of a single glass fiber. No bare fiber segments are visible within the field of view, indicating complete surface coverage. This uniform topology underpins the spatially homogeneous baseline conductivity required for reliable EIT inversion.

Figure 5: Scanning Electron Microscopy picture of a single fiber covered with carbon nanotubes showing the morphology of the manufactured sensors.

3.2 Localized Pressure- Induced Conductivity Changes

Controlled out of plane compression was used as a repeatable, resin free surrogate to evaluate spatial resolution. Figure 6a presents the reconstructed conductivity map produced by a circular footprint; Figure 6b shows the response to a 15×30 mm rectangular footprint. The red outlines in drawn on the sensors represents the physical footprints of the two loading blocks. In both maps the regions of elevated conductivity (warm colors) conform closely to these boundaries, confirming that the single-step Gauss-Newton inversion can localize mechanical stimuli with minimal geometric distortion. The positive $\Delta\sigma$ inside the loaded zones is consistent with the tunnelling model: compression reduces the inter-nanotube spacing, lowers the junction resistance, and therefore raises the apparent bulk conductivity. A narrow band of moderate contrast appears immediately outside each footprint because the veil is a continuous layer and a small portion of the load is redistributed to neighboring fibers. Nevertheless, the principal regions of change remain clearly identifiable.

Figure 6: Reconstructed impedance maps of compression test with (a) circular (b) rectangular applied loading blocks.

3.3 Resin Flow Imaging During VARTM

After tuning the inversion on a controllable load, we next validated the same parameters during an actual infusion. The compression calibration was validated under real processing conditions using the single edge VARTM infusion. Figure 7 contains the video frames (top) with the conductivity maps reconstructed from the 208-voltage data (bottom) at 10, 18 and 30 s after the inlet valve opened. In the EIT images the dark-blue tones mark the zones where conductivity has fallen the most. This reduction is expected: as the epoxy, an electrical insulator, permeates the CNT veil, it fills the pore space between nanotubes, increases the average tunnelling distance, and therefore raises the local resistance (lowers σ). The advancing blue front in the reconstructions tracks the visible resin front in the video within a few millimeters during the first $\approx 80\%$ of the fill, confirming that the opposite drive/sense pattern supplies the mid-field sensitivity needed to image a broad, smoothly curved interface. A faint conductivity gradient surrounds the primary front, reflecting the partial wet-out of the veil ahead of the visually sharp resin line; such “halo” behavior is consistent with capillary wicking of low-viscosity resin into the CNT network before the bulk flow arrives. Only near the end of the run does the reconstructed front overshoot the camera-derived position. At that stage the wetted area occupies a small fraction of the domain, the voltage changes become correspondingly weaker, and the inverse problem grows less well conditioned—conditions under which mild over-prediction is anticipated. Nevertheless, the close agreement throughout most of the infusion confirms that the reconstruction parameters tuned with the compression surrogate translate directly to resin-flow imaging and that the CNT-veil/EIT system is capable of millimeter-scale tracking accuracy under real processing conditions.

Figure 7: The recorded (top) and the reconstructed (bottom) images of VARTM that were taken at (a) 10seconds, (b) 18 seconds and (c) 30 seconds. Dark blue areas represent the resin while lighter colors represent the unwetted areas.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

To conclude, the morphology study verifies a continuous, mechanically robust CNT network; the pressure experiments demonstrate sub-centimeter localization for both circular and rectangular stimuli; and the VARTM trial establishes that these calibration results translate to real time flow front tracking during infusion. The combined evidence supports the use of compression loading as a rapid, consumable free surrogate for EIT parameter optimization and confirms the viability of CNT veil sensors for closed loop control of resin infusion processes.

Future work will explore deliberately engineered flow-front anomalies. Race-tracking channels, edge leaks and heterogeneous fiber-permeability zones will be introduced so that the accuracy of EIT reconstructions can be benchmarked against high-speed video ground truth. On the instrumentation side, the LabVIEW acquisition routine will be linked directly to EIDORS in MATLAB, enabling automated hand-off of each voltage frame for on-the-fly inversion; once this pipeline is established, switching algorithms and current-drive schemes will be optimized to increase the update rate. Parallel efforts will focus on adaptive regularization and mesh-refinement strategies to sharpen spatial resolution without sacrificing robustness, and on multi-frequency excitation to decouple conductivity and permittivity effects during cure. These developments will move the CNT-veil/EIT platform from laboratory demonstration to a practical tool for intelligent control of industrial resin infusion.

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